

Teacher of the "Automation and Control" Department of TMTI:

Mengatova Khurshida Tashmukhamatovna

khurshidamengatova@gmail.com

Teacher of the "Automation and Control" department of TMTI:

Jakhongir Salokhidinov Alisher o'g'li

jakhongir.salokhidinov@gmail.com

Abstract:

Educational technologies are one of the main factors in improving the quality of training of specialists in higher education. In particular, we believe that improving the teaching of subjects in higher education institutions based on the methods of using mobile applications in the educational process, with a new approach to the development of educational technologies in the training of personnel in various fields, will create a basis for achieving high results in increasing the effectiveness of education.

Keywords: WAP, GPRS, EDGE, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Mobile, BOYD.

In the educational system of advanced countries, research aimed at effective use of computer equipment and modern information and communication technologies is ongoing. These circumstances indicate the importance of computer science in the personnel training system. One of the main concepts of computer science is information communication technology. Technology, translated from the Greek (techne), means art, skill, knowledge, which in turn are processes. Processes are a set of certain actions to achieve a set goal.

Mobile learning is a special form of learning that has the ability to combine individual, group and collective learning with curricular and extracurricular activities using mobile technologies. In the educational process, the phrase "Mobile learning" can be interpreted as follows:

- Devices in education (optional mobile devices and network technologies);
- Teacher (in the course of teaching, the device is in the classroom or
- may be located outside the audience);
- Application to the educational process depending on the type of lesson (another school, a virtual teacher on the Internet from two regions of the city). In order to apply mobile teaching to the educational process in a mass way, it is necessary to pay attention to the following organizational and pedagogical requirements:

- Organization of mobile classes based on tablets, netbooks and laptops in educational practice;

Send an opinion

Side panel

History

Sokhranennye

Predlojit perevod

The advantages of mobile learning are:

1. Gives students the opportunity to freely change the place;
2. Enables students with disabilities to study using mobile devices;

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3. There will be no need for a personal computer and paper educational literature;
4. With the help of modern wireless technologies, the distribution of educational resources among users is facilitated (WAP, GPRS, EDGE, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi);
5. Mobile education uses multimedia content, that is, information is expressed in various forms: text, graphics, audio. In such a case, the effectiveness of learning and memorization of educational resources increases, motivation to learn develops. If the learners are interested in completing the tasks, in this case

A volunteer teacher will be able to say without hesitation that the audience will be enlivened, the motivation to learn will develop, and the efficiency of learning will increase.

The use of mobile applications in studying subjects in education, including higher education, along with the above-mentioned results, creates an opportunity for the listener to study without choosing space and time. For example: the implementation of problems and examples in mathematics using the ++ coding application gives a quick, high-quality and accurate answer, encouraging the student to think innovatively. Using the program for calculating the sum of this product, it is possible to get an infinite result.

```
#include <iostream>
#include <cmath>
using namespace std;
int main()
{
    int n;
    double summa_M, summa_X, summa_Y, Q, a, F, l, b, P, R, N;
    cout << "Q = "; cin >> Q;
    cout << "n = "; cin >> n; //n=> buyerda summa yuqori chegarasi
    cout << "a = " << endl; cin >> a;
    cout << "F = " << endl; cin >> F;
    cout << "l = " << endl; cin >> l; //l=> alfa urnida
    cout << "b = " << endl; cin >> b; //b=> betta urnida
    cout << "P = " << endl; cin >> P;
    cout << "R = " << endl; cin >> R;
    cout << "N = " << endl; cin >> N;
    for(int i=1; i<=n; i++)
        summa_M += -Q*a + F*sin(2*i) + P*sin(b)*a + P*cos(b)*2*a + Q*2*a - R*cos(l)*4*a -
        R*sin(a)*2*a + N*sin(b)*4*a + N*cos(b)*2*a;
    summa_X += Q + F*sin(l) + P*cos(b) - Q + R*sin(l) - N*cos(b);
    summa_Y += F*cos(l) - P*sin(b) + R*cos(l) - N*sin(b);
    cout << "summa_M = " << summa_M << endl;
    cout << "summa_X = " << summa_X << endl;
    cout << "summa_Y = " << summa_Y << endl;
    return 0;
}
```



```
10:45 | 0,2KB/s | [Icons]
Coding C++
Auto saved at 10:45:19

#include <iostream>
#include <cmath>
using namespace std;
int main()
{
    int n;
    double summa_M, summa_X, summa_Y, Q, a, F, l, b, P, R, N;
    cout<<"Q = ";cin>>Q;
    cout<<"n = ";cin>>n; //n=>buyurda sur
    cout<<"a = ";cin>>a;
    cout<<"F = ";cin>>F;
    cout<<"l = ";cin>>l; //l=>alfa urnid
    cout<<"b = ";cin>>b; //b=>beta urnid
    cout<<"P = ";cin>>P;
    cout<<"R = ";cin>>R;
    cout<<"N = ";cin>>N;
    for(int i=1; i<=n; i++)

    summa_M+=-Q*a+F*sin(2*l)+P*sin(b)*a;
    summa_X+=Q+F*sin(l)+P*cos(b)-Q+R*sin
    summa_Y+=F*cos(l)-P*sin(b)+R*cos(l)

    cout<<"summa_M ="<<summa_M<<endl;
    cout<<"summa_X ="<<summa_X<<endl;
    cout<<"summa_Y ="<<summa_Y<<endl;
    return 0;
}

10:46 | 0,1KB/s | [Icons]
Compile Result

Q = 22
n = 3
a = 3
F = 44
l = 4
b = 4
P = 5
R = 7
N = 77
summa_M = -nan
summa_X = 8.46541
summa_Y = -3.81441e+220
[Process completed - press Enter]
```

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